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Bringing to life Rigas Velestinlis' Charta of Greece (1796-7) by using Augmented Reality Technology and 3D visualization

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Abstract:

Onassis Library is a special collection historical library created in 2009 by the Onassis Foundation in support of Education and Culture in Athens, Greece. The library opened its doors in 2016 organizing cultural activities and educational programs for all.

One of the most valuable treasures of the library is Charta (Map) of Greece, printed in Vienna in 1796-7 by Rigas Velestinlis, a revolutionary figure of the Greek Enlightenment. It depicts almost the whole of Southeast Europe and is widely considered as the most important example of Greek cartography that inspired the Greek Revolution for Independence in 1821, influencing also neighbouring people in the Balkans. The Charta, besides the traditional depiction of a map of the Balkan Peninsula, includes an extensive array of symbols, figures and pictures, whilst enriching points of this map with information, becoming a "multimedia" piece ahead of its time.

In this paper, an Augmented Reality (AR) educational application for android devices inspired by Rigas' Charta, will be presented, aiming at highlighting those hidden symbols with 3D graphics, visualizing stories and narrating myths depicted in the map, using open-source or low-cost software to enrich the cultural education outcome. This way, a new layer

of information is being revealed at key points of the Charta, as Riga's initial intention was. This application helps library visitors, especially youth and children, to familiarize themselves with the cartographic and archival heritage, through storytelling techniques, educational material and hands-on experience, to explore the hidden tales and myths of the map and its communicative power in an interactive manner. Delving into this cultural document by utilizing new technologies in history learning and promoting of cultural wealth, the interest and motivation of the user is revitalized, with all of the above contributing to an even better understanding of the original purpose of Charta's creation.

Keywords: Augmented Reality applications, cartographic educational activities, gamification, digital humanities, 3D technology and cultural heritage.

ONASSIS LIBRARY EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMS

Onassis Library is a historical library which accumulates important collections of old books, archives, artworks and documents (historical maps, atlases, travel books, geographical editions), providing excellent material for the creation of various learning activities. Since 2016 that it finished its first digitization project and opened its doors to the public, digitally and physically, it became an inexhaustible source of inspiration, encouraging curiosity, discovery and critical thinking, making the cultural heritage of seven centuries accessible to the public through educational and cultural programs.

Picture 1. The Onassis Library (Athens, Greece)

As one of the most important assets of the library is the historical map, Rigas Velestinlis' Charta of Greece, many events have been organized by the library (series of lectures, educational programs for students, families, researchers and people with disabilities) regarding the revolutionary work and the manifold personality of its creator. Moreover, in 2018 a successful and fruitful collaboration with the Cartographic Heritage Archives of General State Archives (GSA) of Greece was initiated, taking the form for an expanded series of upgraded educational activities. All of the expertise, knowledge and experience translated into a range of educational activities with technological orientation. By experimenting with Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), Digital Storytelling, 3D Video Game technologies and

generally contemporary technological techniques applied on historical documents and archives, the outcome was very promising. Students showed a great interest in learning historical and geographical information as they could implement those in digital collaborative projects. This led to the design and production of further digital activities involving this historical map, such as "See the Map through a VR mask", "The secrets of Rigas' Charta", "Hack the Map: Rigas' Charta", "Discovering a historical map with Artbots" and "Paintellings: Travelling with the symbols and the myths of Rigas Charta".

Picture 2. Educational and other cartographic activities related to Rigas' Charta

This persistent occupation with Rigas' Charta, led to the evolution of the above educational activities, generated new ideas and deepened the knowledge regarding this monument of cultural heritage. Rigas' Charta is considered an item of great interest and research on behalf of the GSA-Cartographic Heritage Archives and was used as an example of good practice in many educational programs, workshops and lectures, research notes and other cartographic activities.

Consequently, in 2021, on the occasion of the 200th anniversary of the Greek Struggle for Independence (1821) and responding to the growing interest of the educational community, the Onassis Library, among other projects, created an open access e-book for children 8-12 years old entitled "[Young Rigas and the secret symbols of Charta](#)" in collaboration with the well-known Greek author and illustrator Lida Varvarousi and the GSA-Cartographic Heritage Archives. Since the book was accompanied by a reproduction of Rigas' Charta, it was a great opportunity to publish alongside it the Augmented Reality (AR) application that was developed initially for the Onassis Library visitors and aims to bring to life, in a 3D form, more than 15 depictions engraved on the historical map, making it accessible to a wider audience. Through this holistic approach, a historical document was presented in a comprehensible and contemporary way, motivating the new generation to interact

with the Greek cultural heritage and inspiring them to create their own digital works, involving historical themes and rare artifacts in the learning process.

Picture 3. (Left) The children’s book: “Young Rigas and the secret symbols of Charta”. The book is accompanied with a downscale copy of the Charta (70X70 cm). (Right) Using the AR application, the reader can use the copy of the Charta to explore it, or even visit one of its physical locations and discover its secrets!

THE RIGAS VELESTINLIS' CHARTA (MAP) OF GREECE (VIENNA, 1796-1797)

The Charta of Rigas Velestinlis is one of the most important works of the Neohellenic Enlightenment and the most characteristic sample of Greek cartography of the pre-revolutionary period (Tolias, G., 2010). Printed in 1796-97 in Vienna, it consists of 12 sheets, each measuring approximately 50x70 cm, which, if combined, form a large map with a total dimension of 2x2m. It was created by Rigas Velestinlis (1757-1798) and engraved by Francois Müller, counting 1220 copies. Rigas was a prominent figure of the Greek Enlightenment during the 18th century and contributed to the formation of the ideas and vision that inspired the Greek Revolution of 1821, influencing also the neighbouring people in Balkans with his radical ideas on democracy, freedom and justice.

Rigas intentionally incorporated in his map symbols such as scenes of everyday life in ancient Greece, 162 ancient Greek, Roman and medieval coins, more than 5800 toponyms, archaeological monuments, mythical heroes, comments, historical battles and topographic drawings, deriving from the rich classical and European cartographic and literary tradition, mainly of French origin (Laios 1960, Livieratos, 2008). All these iconographic elements supported Rigas' vision for the establishment of a free democratic State in the Balkan Peninsula, based on the ideas of freedom,

justice and equality and reflected the historical continuity of the Greek culture and civilization from antiquity to the 18th century. The use of symbols incorporates an incredible communicative power, aiming at the awakening of the national identity of the Greeks and all the enslaved people in the Balkans, characterizing the Charta as a “multimedia” of another era (Livieratos, E., 2008). Besides of its value as a revolutionary item, Charta's educational aspect is also of great importance, since it was intended to be used as supportive educational material, reflecting its creator's innovative ideas on high order quality education provided for free in Greek schools in Ottoman Empire and in Europe (Tolias, 2010).

Picture 4. Rigas' Charta of Greece, 2x2 m., 12 map-sheets, Vienna, 1796-7 (left), framed in Onassis Library (top right) and bound as a book in the General State Archives of Greece (bottom right).

Today, there are only 59 copies of this historical map, scattered around the world, in major Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums and private collections. The Onassis Library and the Central Services of General State Archives of Greece have a full copy of the 12-page Charta each.

RIGAS' CHARTA AUGMENTED REALITY APPLICATION

The heroic life of Rigas Velestinlis and the story behind his map creation became the source of inspiration for the development of an augmented reality (AR) application. Using such a technology in history learning processes and cultural heritage approaches, allows students to gather knowledge from multiple different sources, enables ease of access, easy processing and the comparison of data from different time periods. Therefore, passive learning becomes active learning, while collaborative learning, exploratory approaches and problem solving are supported through an Object Based Learning (OBL) approach. New features are provided as to how to visualize the educational material and interact with the user in an intuitive manner.

The pedagogical goal of this digital project was to motivate the new generation to decode the iconographic wealth of the Charta by using new technology tools. By involving historical artifacts in the learning process, the library visitors and the app users in general are encouraged to interact with the Greek cartographic heritage. Transferring the Charta's treasures outside of the Onassis Library through the AR app, knowledge distribution was encouraged by expanding the original content of this important document, which was already a multimedia map ahead of its time. Through gamification one can learn the history of the creation of the Charta and the meaning of the symbols that are engraved on it.

By using mixed reality technologies for educational purposes there is the advantage of a very direct approach that is strengthening participation. Exploratory learning is encouraged which in its turn contributes to the understanding and the consolidation of new knowledge. Visualization helps in understanding difficult or abstract concepts, especially for visual learners. The basic principles of constructive learning, experiential learning (ExL) and discovery learning are combined and delivered through a rewarding system, a characteristic element of video games, which greatly encourages the learning process.

As for the creation of the application itself, the process was divided in several stages. The first stage was the research and collection of material, based mainly on the iconographic wealth of the Charta itself and on various historical sources. Following this, an initial selection of 15 stories was made, prioritised with emphasis on their educational value. Then, an evaluation and filtering of the most appropriate material was conducted and initial scenarios were created based on the findings. A further step included the clean-up process, digitization and editing of the raw material deriving from original physical sources. Additionally, since AR is based on user-defined images for the story depiction, the evaluation of the tracking strength of the related tracker images per symbol and its calibration was necessary in order to achieve solid tracking results.

Picture 5. Tracking quality sample for the AR application.

Afterwards, the creation process followed, where original 2D artwork was created from combining classical representations of famous incidents and adjusting them in

the context of a unified art style that would be apply to all the elements of the Charta. Those were processed and cut in pieces in order to be animated and placed in a hierarchy inside the Unity 3D engine, where the final result was combined. Loopable animations were created for most stories with random offsets in order to enrich variation whilst keeping the project optimized for mobile devices. Scenes from the Charta were also used and were brought to life by using the same 2D technique or by utilizing a 3D skeleton (bones) in order to be animated, like for example Heracles and the Amazon.

Picture 6. A combination of a 2D drawing from the Charta with 3D geometry, in order to obtain 3D bones and animation.

For certain stories, 3D models optimized for mobile usage were created and exported with custom animations into the Unity 3D game engine. The final material and texture setup took place inside of Unity, with mobile-optimized materials. Animations were either created entirely inside of Unity and were initiated via code, or they were imported from the 3D modelling software, ready as loops. Additionally, some simple geometry objects, such as the coins, were created directly inside of Unity engine.

Combining all of the above inside of the Unity 3D engine, each tracker image was handled like a separate scene. For each scene, usually a three-point lighting setup was used. A background music track was applied throughout the application and various sound effects per image were created and called via scripting, as well as narrations to certain events, when necessary. Some additional effects, such as particle effects were created in order to depict flames or dust for example. Finally, some graphic elements were designed for the presentation of the app whilst maintaining a unified aesthetic look.

Picture 7. The Colossus of Rhodes, the 3D model was optimized whereas additional effects were added inside Unity3D, such as particles for the torch.

Picture 8. The end result inside of the Unity 3D game engine, before the application build.

The application initially focuses on over fifteen symbols depicted on the Rigas' Charta that are presented in the form of 2D and 3D animated visualizations. The app can be used with all copies and versions of the map, both physical and digital. The user is triggered to explore this historical document, to discover the 3D animated stories and unveil their hidden symbolism. Some of those icons are: 1) The 162 ancient and medieval coins, 2) Jason and the Argo, 3) Heracles and the Amazon, 4) The ancient Greek theatre, 5) Ancient Olympia and the Olympic games, 6) Delphi, 7) Colossus of Rhodes, 8) Pyrrha and Deucalion, 9) The female figure on the forehead, 10) Hero and Leander, 11) The battle of Plataea, 12) The naval battle of Salamis, 13) The battle of Thermopylae, 14) The sleeping lion, 15) The wind rose.

Picture 9. Some of the symbols of Rigas' Charta in 3D visual form (Rigas' Charta AR app – creator: Kostas Diamantis)

Through this application, children and adults alike have the opportunity to interact with a historical document in a playful and creative way. They are motivated to search for the secret symbols that Rigas printed on the map, to recognize them and to learn their meaning. At the same time, this game of hidden treasure is an entertaining experience that creates images and emotions that can remain for a long time after the end of the educational activity.

It has been observed that by using historical objects in education (Object Based Learning) it enhances and makes the learning process more effective (Romanek & Lynch, 2008). OBL offers an interactive experience for students, challenging them to critically address a variety of topics, interacting with each other and paying greater attention to the subject (Hannan et al., 2013). This approach allows the student to explore ideas, processes and events related to the subject and to further link these observations to complex ideas and abstract concepts. In addition, it mediates and enhances learning, facilitating the substantive and in-depth understanding of a cognitive area (Freeman et al., 2014) leading to a long-term outcome in relation to memory (Romanek & Lynch, 2008; 284). This result is magnified and transformed into a unique experience when combined with Games Based Learning (GBL), where game elements (points, rewards, leaderboards, competition, achievements) are applied in a learning environment designed by educators. This methodology increases the motivation for learning even more, strengthens the ability to problem solving and enhances a greater understanding (Gee, 2005).

Game-based learning does not replace traditional learning but is considered as an alternative means that is attractive to young people, motivating them to acquire

knowledge and skills in teaching topics that are considered "difficult", painful or boring (Papadakis & Kalogiannakis, 2019). According to research, it seems that as the student's performance in the game improves, so does one's decision-making skills, while positive reactions and emotions that contribute to learning prevail (Squire, 2006).

onassis.link/rigas-velestinlis-charta

Picture 10. The link to the official page of the Application, Rigas' Charta

CONCLUSION

Digital applications today are applied in a wide range of educational fields. Their creative combination with history, geography, cartography and visual arts provide advanced tools and unlimited potential for collecting, researching and presenting facts, evidence and data. This dynamic relationship of new technologies alongside teaching and learning has changed the way we receive and process information and has unleashed the possibilities of reviving the past.

At the same time, the celebration of the 200th anniversary of the Greek Struggle for Independence (1821-2021) renewed the interest on behalf of the educational community, for the original 18th c. literary, archival and cartographic production, creating ideal conditions for Libraries and Archives to promote their collections. Moreover, creative collaborations between Libraries, Archives and University Departments are multiplying the benefits of gained experience and expertise, broadening the profile and the age group of its audience.

The interaction with a digital item alone cannot be compared to the experiential visit in a museum or a library, thus the ideal scenario would be to combine these two forms of experience for a greater end result. The new AR application on Rigas' Charta succeeds in unifying the fields of information technology, history, geography, cartography, visual arts and museum education. The utilization of digital works inspired by historical objects motivate students to interact with their cultural heritage in an interesting and playful way, promoting dialogue and collaboration between them. Also, the educational approaches addressed to younger children (8-12 years old), allow for an initial contact with important historical items of cultural heritage in a map-friendly and archival-friendly, creative way and help to promote the early cultivation of archival consciousness (Hatziganni 2012, Sarra 2018).

The feedback regarding the AR application was positive and was greatly received, especially by the educational community. Many Libraries and Museums which own a copy of Rigas' Charta, inquired about it. This digital project managed to combine the digital world with the humanities and make our cultural heritage accessible to the general public. Through this experience we managed to preserve and reinterpret

historical material and primary sources in new digital ways for future generations, hacking standard practices, thinking outside the box and extending their social and educational benefits. This new digital route showed that it could broaden and enrich the way we perceive history in the future. The wide availability of open-source, free or educational license software enables more people than ever to create experiences that can digitally enrich material related to cultural heritage and make it available to a wider global audience.

The Rigas' Charta AR application strengthened the emotional involvement of children with a historical document and cultivated a positive attitude and enthusiasm towards the learning process, enriching history and geography lessons, promoting cartographic cultural heritage through the use of innovative technical tools in education. The awareness of the need to devise new teaching methods that appeal to demanding students, in addition to the usage of digital games, has further led to the adoption of gamification as a learning methodology, focusing on disguising an existing learning process so that users perceive it as a game (Landers, Auer, Collmus & Armstrong, 2018). The gamification approach was successfully implemented in the Rigas' Charta AR app, encouraging creative thinking, allowing discovery learning and giving the user the feelings of surprise and excitement. The importance of this approach focuses not only on the rewards (Kapp, 2012), but on the interesting combination of real and virtual worlds, the immersive mixed reality experiences, the satisfaction of the unexpected and the joy of discovering hidden symbols and meanings.

Finally, the AR application, managed to bring out of the obscurity a significant cultural wealth, to enrich and animate it and to motivate students and teachers to rediscover the treasures of Greek spiritual tradition, to unlock hidden secrets and to highlight historical sources and rare works, with the help of technology, storytelling, iconography and visual art creation. Furthermore, the creative engagement with the original map led to a deeper understanding of its significance and its connection with the vision and the other publishing works of Rigas Velestinlis.

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References

- Chatterjee, H.J. & Hannan, L. (2015). *Engaging the Senses: Object-Based Learning in Higher Education*. London: Routledge
- Daskalakis, A. (1937). *Righas Velestinlis, la Revolution Française et les preludes de la Revolution Hellenique*, Paris.
- Dieli Marta (2020) *Antiquity and Enlightenment Culture*, ed. Felicity Loughlin and Alexandre Johnston. *The Enlightenment and the teaching of Ancient Greek Grammar in Greece*, p. 176-177.
- Edmonds Elizabeth M. (2020). *The Victorian Biographer of Rigas*, Georgia Gotsi, Institute of Historical Research (IHR/NHRF)

Freeman, S., Eddy, S.L., McDonough, M., Smith, M.K., Okoroafor, N., Jordt, H., and Wenderoth, M.P. (2014). Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences USA* 111, 8410-8415

Gahan, A. (2013). *3ds Max Modeling for Games: Insider's Guide to Game Character, Vehicle, and Environment Modeling*, CRC Press.

Guiomar J.-Y. & M.-T. Lorain (2006). La carte de Grèce de Rigas et le nom de la Grèce, *Annales Historiques de la Revolution Française*, Numéro 319, <http://ahrf.revues.org/document106.html>

Gutierrez, M., et al. (2008). *Stepping into Virtual Reality*, Springer London.

Haydn, T. (2013). *Using New Technologies to Enhance Teaching and Learning in History*, Taylor & Francis.

Hatzigianni, K. (2012). Educational Activities from the General State Archives of Greece: Exam-ples of Implementation, in: Vakalopoulou M. Ch, N. E. Karapidakis (ed.), *Αρχαιονομία. The Prac-tices of General State Archives of Greece*, Athens 2012 (In Greek).

Laios, G. (1960). "Οι Χάρτες του Ρήγα. Έρευνα επί νέων πηγών", *Δελτίον Ιστορικής και Εθνολογικής Εταιρείας Ελλάδος*, τ. 14., :231-312 (In Greek).

Livieratos, E. (2007). "Digital analysis of cartographic heritage", invited presentation at the International Cartographic Association session: Teaching history of cartography, Bern, 7 July, 22nd International Conference on History of Cartography.

Livieratos, E. (2008). On the cartography of Rigas Charta, *e-Perimtron*, Vol. 3, No. 3 [120-145]

Pazarli, M., N. Ploutoglou, K. Papadopoulos, A. Tsorlini, E. Livieratos, 2007. "Digital approaches to Righas Veletinlis' Charta, the 18th century cartographic monument of Greek cultural heritage", XXIII International Cartographic Conference, Moscow, 4-10 August 2007, re: http://cartography.web.auth.gr/Righas/Moscow_Righas.htm.

Pazarli, M. (2014). *Rigas Veletinlis' Map (Charta) of Greece: A cartographic approach*, PhD the-sis, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, <https://ikee.lib.auth.gr/record/134409/files/GRI-2014-12434.pdf>

Romanek, D. & Lynch, B. (2008). "Touch and the Value of Object Handling: Final Conclusions for a New Sensory Museology." In Chatterjee, H. J. (Ed.) *In Touch in Museums: Policy and Practice in Object Handling*. Oxford & New York: Berg.

Sarra, Ch. (2018). Archival Resources as an Integral Parameter of Educational Processes. Presentation to the workshop « `...εις ο φυλάσσεται το αρχείο του Σχολείου'. Searching the archives of our school, 1929-1989», Historical Archives Group, ESUA, Athens, 19/5/2018, <http://www.pspa.eu/index.php/drastiriotites-pspa/mathitikoi-omiloi/69-mathitikoi-omiloi-2017-18/136-omilos-istorikis-erevna-arxeiou-pspa> (In Greek).

Schönborn, K. J. & Anderson, T. R. (2006). The Importance of visual literacy in the education of biochemists. *Biochemistry and Molecular Biology Education*, 34, 94-102.

Sinicki, A. (2017). *Learn Unity for Android Game Development: A Guide to Game Design, Development, and Marketing*, Apress.

Tolias, G. (2008). Antiquarianism, Patriotism and Empire. Transfer of the cartography of the Travels of Anacharsis the Younger, 1788-1811, *e-Perimetron*, Vol.3, No 3 [101-119].

Tolias, G. (2010). Αποχαιρετισμός στο Γένος. Αυτοκρατορία και πατριωτισμός στο χαρτογραφικό έργο του Ρήγα (1796-97), *Χάρτα της Ελλάδος*, Ν. Κ. Κομνηνός (επιμ.), Αθήνα (In Greek).

Ubicini J.-H. A. (1881). *La Grande Carte par Rhigas, Révue de Géographie*, dixième livraison.

Van Arnhem, J. P., et al. (2018). *Augmented and Virtual Reality in Libraries*, Rowman & Littlefield Publishers.

Yelland, N. (2006). *Shift to the Future: Rethinking Learning with New Technologies in Education*, Taylor & Francis.